

Legionary apologia in contemporary Romania: Advancing a comparative methodology for scaling European fascisms

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Abstract

This article investigates the political resurgence of radical fascist ideologies in contemporary Romania, specifically those associated with the Legionary Movement and the Antonescian ideology. The inquiry is framed within the context of the disputed 2024 presidential elections, later annulled, which had initially resulted in a victory for Călin Georgescu. The article presents a legal evaluation of the criteria for typicality concerning the criminal charges brought against Georgescu by the General Prosecutor's Office (public glorification of individuals convicted of genocide, crimes against humanity, and war crimes, the promotion of fascist, legionary, racist, or xenophobic ideas, concepts, or doctrines). Based on a semi-quantitative doctrinal assessment of European fascist typologies (hybrid, classical, radical, and totalitarian) from 1922 to 1975, five core attributes linked to the systemic criminality of each regime are coded. The findings show Romania as one of the most exterminatory fascist regimes in Europe, ranking just below Nazi Germany: Legionary Movement (7.6 out of 10 on the political violence scale) and Antonescu regime (8.0 out of 10). This ranking makes Georgescu's promotion of Legionary and Antonescian rhetoric particularly disquieting from both a political and criminal standpoint. The analysis of ideological convergence between 11 classical analytical variables of European fascism and Georgescu's political discourse yields an average score of 5.8 out of 10, placing Georgescu's position between moderate and high levels in relation to the characteristics of classical European fascism (Italian Mussolini ideology and Spanish Francoism).

Keywords

Călin Georgescu; Corneliu Zelea Codreanu; Ion Antonescu; fascism; Legionary ideology

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Introduction

Prior to a sudden surge in online visibility, just two weeks before the first round of the presidential election on November 24, 2024, Călin Georgescu occupied no significant role within Romania's political landscape². Up until the exit poll results were announced on the evening of November 24, Georgescu remained a true political outsider – lacking visibility and, implicitly, any credible prospects. He was part of the familiar cohort of fringe candidates who routinely crowd national elections in any democratic system, including Romania's presidential elections within its republican constitutional framework.

Without exception, everyone was utterly stunned by Georgescu's victory in the first round of the presidential elections on November 24, 2024. The independent candidate, whom no one had ever credited with a genuine political chance, secured first place with 2,120,401 votes, amounting to 22.94% of the valid ballots. In second place came the mayor of Câmpulung, Elena Lasconi, president of the Save Romania Union (USR), with 1,772,500 votes, amounting to 19.18% of the valid ballots. Lasconi's qualification for the presidential runoff, surpassing the leaders of the two main ruling parties, Marcel Ciolacu (Social Democratic Party, PSD) and Nicolae Ciucă (National Liberal Party, PNL), was also a huge surprise. Thus, two outsiders (Georgescu and Lasconi) won the first round of the 2024 presidential elections against the prime ministers of Romania (Ciolacu and Ciucă).

Since no candidate obtained an absolute majority, a second round of the presidential elections was to be organized on December 8, 2024, between Georgescu and Lasconi. However, the elections were annulled on December 6, 2024 by the Constitutional Court of Romania³, following the review of documents prepared by the intelligence services which raised suspicions regarding the existence of electoral irregularities committed by the independent candidate Georgescu. The briefing notes of the Romanian intelligence structures were declassified on December 4, 2024, by the Presidential Administration⁴, after their presentation and discussion on November 28, 2024, within the Supreme Council of National Defence of Romania (CSAT)⁵.

² As stated in the indictment issued by the Public Prosecutor's Office on July 1, 2025 (prepared by the Chief Prosecutor Marius Iacob of the Criminal Investigation Service within the Criminal Investigation Division of the Prosecutor's Office attached to the High Court of Cassation and Justice), in case no. 2226/221/P/2023/d1, in which Călin Georgescu is the defendant, between November 13 and 26, 2024, Călin Georgescu, being backed by more than 100 influencers with a combined audience exceeding 8 million active followers, achieved the performance of ranking 9th globally in TikTok's trending charts for video content promoting his candidacy in the presidential elections (https://www.luju.ro/static/files/2025/iulie/01/rechizitoriu_calin_georgescu.pdf).

³ *Decision No. 32 of the Constitutional Court of Romania*, dated December 6, 2024, regarding the annulment of the electoral process for the election of the President of Romania in 2024, published the same day in the Official Gazette of Romania No. 1231 (https://www.ccr.ro/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/Hotarare_32_2024.pdf).

⁴ The press release which declassified and disclosed reports from the Romanian intelligence services regarding potential national security risks related to the November 24, 2024 elections, is available at <https://www.presidency.ro/ro/media/comunicate-de-presa/comunicat-de-presa1733327193>.

⁵ The press release of November 28, 2024, regarding the assessment by the Supreme Council of National Defence (CSAT) of potential national security risks in connection with the presidential elections of November 24, 2024, was prepared on the basis of intelligence service reports. These determined that hostile cyber operations against Romania had occurred, carried out by both state and non-state actors (including the Russian Federation, explicitly named but without supporting evidence, as seeking to erode Romania's social cohesion), with the objective of influencing the electoral process. The release states that "by violating electoral legislation, one presidential candidate benefited from massive exposure, due to the preferential treatment granted by the TikTok platform, which failed to label him as a political candidate and did not require him to tag his video campaign materials with the unique identification code assigned by the Permanent Electoral Authority upon the appointment of the

On November 28, 2024, the Supreme Council of National Defence of Romania (CSAT) indicated that TikTok's algorithmic overexposure of Georgescu played a decisive role in his victory in Romania's presidential election. In this interpretation, the candidate favored by TikTok emerged, through digital obscurity, as the apparent choice of the Romanian electorate. The idea that TikTok yields Mephistophelian technology capable of conjuring a future president from the "foam of the sea" and "enthroning" him at the Cotroceni Palace, while enticing as a Hollywood storyline, is simplistic, unrealistic, somewhat exaggerated, and even absurd. Following the Presidential Administration's decision on December 4, 2024, to bring the secret services (the General Directorate for Internal Protection of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the Romanian Intelligence Service, the Foreign Intelligence Service, and the Special Telecommunications Service) into the electoral spotlight, the once Hollywood-style scenario is starting to take on the elements of a Bollywood production. In short, the entire Romanian state establishment officially accused, an independent candidate of having conducted his electoral campaign, with alleged irregularities and incorrectness (which are traditionally reproached, in general, to all competitors), in the only place in Romania where he had unrestricted access, that is, on TikTok⁶. Undoubtedly, declassified intelligence reports indicate that the full extent of the privately funded resources supporting Georgescu's candidacy – an online campaign valued at approximately €1,000,000, driven by the coordinated and algorithmic use of 25,000 TikTok accounts managed via a Telegram channel accessed by roughly 1,000 users up to the presidential elections of November 24, 2024 – was negligible when compared to the substantial state-funded allocations made

coordinating financial representative, as mandated by electoral law" (*Press release of November 28, 2024*). In conclusion, "the visibility of that candidate increased significantly compared to other candidates who were recognized by TikTok's algorithms as presidential contenders, and whose promoted content was heavily filtered, exponentially reducing their visibility among platform users" (*Press release of November 28, 2024*, <https://csat.presidency.ro/ro/comuni/sedinta-consiliului-suprem-de-aparare-a-tarii1732806302>).

⁶ Romania's intelligence services raised suspicions regarding the involvement of a foreign state actor (mentioning the Russian Federation) in the presidential elections. This actor allegedly interfered maliciously with the electoral process through a network of approximately 25,000 TikTok accounts. These accounts, associated with Georgescu's campaign, were coordinated via the Russian messaging app Telegram. In particular, the channel @propagatorcg (created in June 2024 and described as "Propagator – Get involved, Romania's Renaissance, Food, Water, Energy") was used, growing from 1,088 subscribers on election day to 5,005 users by December 1, 2024, the date of the parliamentary elections. Many of these accounts had been created as early as 2016 but were activated only two weeks prior to the presidential election. Nearly 800 TikTok accounts had remained inactive until November 11, 2024, after which they were deployed at full operational capacity. TikTok is criticized for not labeling Georgescu as a political candidate, granting him preferential treatment and increasing his exposure compared to other officially registered presidential candidates. Georgescu's visibility on the platform resulted from a sophisticated, orchestrated campaign exploiting algorithms and multiple accounts, accompanied by large-scale promotion, apparently financed from external sources, with estimated expenditures of USD 381,000 in a single month, carried out without legal transparency. As a result, Georgescu experienced a sharp rise between November 13 and 26, 2024, reaching 9th place globally in TikTok's trending videos. This surge was not deemed artificial, as hundreds of millions of views were recorded, especially after his victory in the first round of the presidential election. Additionally, more than 85,000 cyberattacks from 33 countries were detected targeting the IT systems supporting the electoral infrastructure (Permanent Electoral Authority, Special Telecommunications Service), with attempts to exfiltrate access credentials for "bec.ro," "roaep.ro," and "registrulelectoral.ro." Ultimately, Georgescu is accused of benefiting from opaque and unregistered campaign financing. Although he officially reported an electoral budget of zero lei, intelligence services identified donations for online campaign promotion exceeding 1 million euros, from undeclared sources (*Press release of December 4, 2024*).

available to his principal rivals, Ciolacu (incumbent Prime Minister and PSD president) and Ciucă (former Prime Minister and PNL president)⁷. In terms of resources allocated for the 2024 electoral campaign, the disparity between Georgescu and his main rivals⁸ exceeds a ratio of 1 to 10. Such a disproportion can only be likened to the biblical struggle of David against Goliath – albeit a Goliath replicated many times over would be more appropriate. Regarding the presumed support gained from a foreign state actor in favor of Georgescu, Romanian authorities have not produced tangible evidence confirming Russia’s involvement in the 2024 presidential campaign; instead, they have limited themselves to articulating suspicions.

Following the annulment of the presidential elections by the Constitutional Court of Romania on December 6, 2024, the Prosecutor General’s Office initiated legal proceedings against Georgescu. Several criminal investigations were launched, which remain ongoing at the time of writing this article (August 2025), focusing on alleged electoral criminal offenses⁹. Subsequently, on August 4, 2025, Georgescu was formally charged, including with complicity in an attempted coup d’état¹⁰.

What remains deeply concerning for the Romanian society as a whole, particularly for its political sphere, the judiciary, and the intelligence services, is the persistent misinterpretation of the electorate’s intent: Romanians voted for Georgescu not because of his TikTok campaign, but to express their discontent with the political establishment and the mainstream parties, PSD and PNL. 2024 saw a surprise candidate, Georgescu, transformed into a privileged collector of political dissatisfaction. The reason lies in the fact that, during Klaus Iohannis’s second term at the Cotroceni Palace (2019–2024),

⁷ From the public subsidy of €32 million received from the state budget in 2023 by the mainstream parties (PSD and PNL), approximately €20 million was spent on unmarked political advertising in the media (see <https://romania.europalibera.org/a/partide-bani-presa-propaganda-lege-neschimbata/32897063.html>). The public subsidy allocated from the state budget to PSD and PNL in 2024 increased sharply, by more than €20 million, reaching a historic high of nearly €55 million (see <https://romania.europalibera.org/a/subventii-partide-2024-cheltuieli/33259025.html>). Half of this amount, €28 million, was spent on unmarked propaganda in the media during the first 10 months of 2024 (see <http://www.banipartide.ro/subventii>). In this context, the double standard of the Romanian state is notable: it has never sanctioned the illegal advertising carried out by PSD and PNL through improper labeling in the media, yet it reproaches the independent candidate Călin Georgescu – who allegedly employed similar methods on TikTok during the 2024 electoral campaign.

⁸ The (ridiculous and pointless) campaign to raise the political visibility of candidate Nicolae Ciucă – by saturating the country with billboards promoting a book titled “A Soldier in the Service of the Country”, which the former Prime Minister and PNL president is presumed to have authored – cost at least twice as much (€2.5 million) as the total financial support (€1 million) allegedly received by the independent candidate Georgescu, according to intelligence services (see <https://snoop.ro/pretul-cartii-lui-ciuca-3-000-de-exemplare-tiparite-si-promovate-cu-25-milioane-de-euro>).

⁹ For more information on how the international press reported on the hearing of Georgescu before the Prosecutor General’s Office in this context, see <https://www.news.ro/externe/update-presa-internationala-consemneaza-audierea-candidatului-pro-rus-calin-georgescu-in-contextul-anchetei-privind-anularea-alegerilor-prezidentiale-1922400726002025021521946982>.

¹⁰ For more information regarding the charges brought against Călin Georgescu by the Prosecutor General’s Office – namely, two counts related to the offense of committing acts against the constitutional order and the continuous dissemination of false information – the analysis published by HotNews.ro is available <https://hotnews.ro/calin-georgescu-chemat-din-nou-la-parchetul-general-dupa-ce-procurorii-au-audiat-18-mercenari-din-gruparea-lui-horatiu-potra-2037704>. As of August 2025, at the time of writing this article, no final court ruling had been issued in the case of Georgescu, and he remains protected by the constitutional presumption of innocence.

the mainstream parties became cartelized and oligarchized in the exercise of power, while the rotation of the office of Prime Minister between PSD and PNL functioned seamlessly. Throughout this period, the President of Romania appeared to confine his role to ceremonial duties, functioning primarily as the country's foremost "tourist". Multiple luxury aircraft were leased at a cost of €15 million to facilitate the President's unrestricted travel abroad, ostensibly for official visits that, in reality, brought no diplomatic, financial, geopolitical, geostrategic, or economic benefit to Romania¹¹. Consequently, Romanian voters sought to electorally penalize the perceived arrogance of PSD and PNL, which was evident both in their governance and in the conduct of the presidency held by PNL. In response, many cast their votes for Georgescu as an expression of political frustration.

The victory of the TikTok candidate in the Romanian presidential election sent shockwaves in the national and international media. Georgescu's success was all the more surprising since everyone, including his voters, would only become aware of him after he won the elections, a fact that may seem paradoxical in a mature society. Georgescu was virtually unknown before the night of November 24, 2024. From that moment onward, the world, whether euphoric or apprehensive, enthusiastic or anxious, was left questioning the identity of the individual whom Romanians had unexpectedly chosen as their president, a candidate who won the election with minimal campaign expenditure¹². The media around the world immediately began to label him, in keeping with the usual practice of political journalism, as an ultranationalist, populist, right-wing extremist, pro-Russian, or critic towards NATO.

After November 24, 2024, the Romanian society was taken aback as a flood of previously overlooked content surfaced from the depths of the internet, content that Georgescu had consistently promoted over time via various interviews and podcasts. This material included a wide array of controversial claims, scientific inaccuracies, historical distortions, demonstrably false statements, conspiracy theories, gross misinformation, naive mysticism, emphatic absurdities, sensationalist rhetoric, scandalous exaggerations, and hallucinatory commentary, all of which had gone largely unnoticed until his unexpected rise to prominence. Before the date of winning the presidential elections, all these astonishing statements were completely obscure, without any significant social or political impact. Among other claims, Georgescu explicitly and unequivocally stated that he had interacted with beings from an extraterrestrial realm ("I met another species, in no case a human species"); that the nanochips in Pepsi "enter your body the same way they would a laptop"; that humans never reached the moon and the moon landing was a manipulation; that the Egyptian pyramids were not used for their intended purpose; that birth by caesarean section breaks the divine thread; that Lucian Blaga is banned in Romania; that water is not H₂O, but rather information and spirit; that the SARS-CoV-2 virus does not exist, because no one has ever seen it; that the only true science in the world is Jesus Christ; that Proto-Romanian was the root of the Latin language, not the other way around; that the globalists seeking world control are not a human species; and that very soon, humans will no longer use phones but will communicate through telepathy – just as plants, birds, animals, and life itself supposedly did on Earth during the time of Stephen the Great, prince of Moldavia (1457-1504). Georgescu described Corneliu Zelea Codreanu as a genius and characterized the Legionary Movement as a unique phenomenon on planet Earth, claiming it elevated individual consciousness to

¹¹ For more information about President Klaus Iohannis' travel costs abroad, see <https://romania.europalibera.org/a/avioane-private-inchiriate-de-iohannis/33352504.html>.

¹² I have to reassert that the sum of €1 million, which Georgescu is accused of not declaring by the intelligence services, is negligible when compared to the tens of millions of euros reportedly circulated by his main opponents, Ciolacu and Ciucă (press release of December 4, 2024).

the level of national sovereignty. He also asserted that history is false and, specifically, that the captain of the Iron Guard had no involvement in the actions commonly attributed to him, namely, the ordered assassinations. Georgescu argued that, much like Jesus Christ, Codreanu was a dangerous figure and was ultimately eliminated through betrayal¹³.

To any reasonable observer, such preposterous assertions represent glaring aberrations. Only a political harlequin like Georgescu could advance such baseless speculations, which directly clash even with the scientific understanding expected of a middle school student. As never before, the national political scene turned into a *commedia dell'arte*, where costumed and masked cabotins, improvised harlequins, emerged victorious presidential elections. Across several episodes, Romanians watched, either with delight or dismay, depending on their electoral preferences, the remarkable performance skills and theatrical flair of presidential candidate Georgescu. Notably, he often mimicked characters from J.R.R. Tolkien's *The Lord of the Rings*. In December 2024, Georgescu imitated the elf queen Galadriel, when he told his admirers, in a melancholic tone, after the annulment of the elections, that the world had changed, that it was no longer what it used to be, which could be felt *in the rippling of the water, in the rustling of the forest, in the breath of the wind, in the vibration of the earth*. In May 2025, the TikTok candidate reproduced the speech Gandalf, when he told supporters disappointed by the election results *to cry, but not despair, because not all tears are bad*. In February 2025, he replaced Japanese mythology from the introductory part of the film *The Last Samurai* by Edward Zwick (2003), with Dacian mythology, after which he narrated the rest of the text unchanged, in an open display of intellectual imposture¹⁴.

In Romania, the jester was poised to become king or, more likely, a grotesque tyrant, if we are to follow the archetypal model regarded as classical since antiquity. However, society, including politics, does not criminalize foolishness, comedy, and even madness unless they are accompanied by actual crimes. The issue for Georgescu emerged when some of his antics, both humorous and scandalous,

¹³ Additional insights into Georgescu's contentious remarks may be found by consulting the following public sources: Europa FM, Antena 3 CNN, G4Media, and Cristian Hagi (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bSAQaAxtel>, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YH9fgEMXJYc>, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yi2qzx_OdfY, and <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xQbp6ug09A>).

¹⁴ The paragraph about traditional Japan, as expressed by the character Simon Graham ("They say that Japan was created by a sword. They say that the ancient gods dipped a coral blade in the ocean, and when they took it out, four perfect drops fell back into the sea, and those drops became the islands of Japan. I say that Japan was created by a group of people, warriors willing to give their lives for what seems to have become a forgotten word: honour") becomes, in the plagiarized expression of Georgescu, a fraudulent and unintentionally parodic attempt to pay homage to Dacia, as the cradle of the civilization of the Romanian people, by imitating the Japanese text ("Romania was created by the energy given by Zalmoxis, the supreme god of our Geto-Dacian ancestors. 2500 years ago, 7 units of consciousness broke away from the energy condensed 5 million years ago. They broke away to embody and shape a new evolutionary meaning to our civilization. One of the 7 was embodied in Romania and it was called Zalmoxis. I believe that Romania was created by a handful of brave warriors and worthy people who gave their lives for a word that seems forgotten today: honour"). Regarding the political speeches of Georgescu during which he imitates lines inspired by famous films, see G4Media.ro, Hotnews.ro, and Libertatea (<https://www.g4media.ro/video-calin-georgescu-nou-mesaj-inspirat-din-vrajitorul-gandalf-din-stapanul-inelelor-plangeti-dragii-mei-dar-nu-deznadajduiti-nu-toate-lacrimile-sunt-rele-val-de-ironii-onlin.html>, <https://hotnews.ro/calin-georgescu-inca-un-discurs-cu-replici-copiate-dintr-un-film-razboinici-viteji-care-si-au-dat-viata-pentru-un-cuvant-ce-azi-pare-uitat-1896094>, and <https://www.libertatea.ro/stiri/calin-georgescu-a-plagiat-o-pe-regina-elfa-galadriel-din-stapanul-inelelor-intr-un-videoclip-in-care-vorbeste-despre-cum-s-a-schibat-lumea-nu-mai-este-ce-a-fost-5118215>).

began to intersect with the Criminal Code. This refers to his glorification of Romania's legionary past, an act legally classified as a criminal offense. Thus, the Prosecutor General's Office re-enters the scene. By the Public Ministry Indictment of July 1, 2025, drawn up by Chief Prosecutor Marius Iacob from the Criminal Investigation Service of the Criminal Investigation Division of the Prosecutor's Office attached to the High Court of Cassation and Justice, Georgescu was officially indicted and sent to trial in file no. 2226/221/P/2023/d1. He was charged under Article 5 of Government Emergency Ordinance (OUG) 31/2002 with publicly promoting the cult of persons convicted of crimes of genocide, crimes against humanity, and war crimes, as well as with publicly promoting fascist, legionary, racist, or xenophobic ideas, concepts, or doctrines. On August 4, 2025, Georgescu was additionally indicted under Article 397 of the Criminal Code for complicity in an attempted coup d'état – acts committed against the constitutional order – supplementing the initial indictment issued under Article 5 of Government Emergency Ordinance (OUG) 31/2002.

Research questions, objectives, hypotheses, and scientific tools

This study explores the underlying factors contributing to the revival of Legionary ideology in contemporary Romania, a phenomenon reintroduced into public discourse by Călin Georgescu in the context of the (annulled) presidential elections scheduled for November 24, 2024. The study seeks to evaluate three scientific hypotheses, each derived from a set of guiding research questions. First, it is entirely valid to question whether the actions attributed to Georgescu, classified by the Prosecutor General's Office under Article 5 of OUG 31/2002 and Article 397 of the Criminal Code, truly align with the standard definitions of these offenses in contemporary criminal law. To address this doctrinal uncertainty, I have developed a research instrument, presented in Table 1, which this analysis aims to validate. Its purpose is to assess the conditions of typicality relevant to the charges brought against Georgescu.

If the first scientific hypothesis is confirmed, a second research question arises naturally: how serious is the public promotion of the cult of individuals guilty of genocide, crimes against humanity, and war crimes, as well as the public endorsement of fascist, legionary, racist, or xenophobic ideas, conceptions, or doctrines? In an effort to compare Romanian far-right movements with their European counterparts, Table 2 presents a semi-quantitative evaluation of the typology of European fascisms, classified as hybrid, classical, radical, and totalitarian, spanning the period from 1922 to 1975. This assessment uses doctrinal scoring based on five essential characteristics that define the structural criminality of these political regimes: authoritarian control, racial ideology, repression of the opposition, systemic crimes, and military expansionism.

If the research instrument in Table 2 is validated, it becomes necessary to critically examine the degree of ideological convergence between the core historical features of classical European fascism and the legionary-inspired political discourse of the sovereigntist candidate Georgescu, who, from a criminal standpoint, committed the criminal offense of campaigning using elements of Legionary propaganda. This assessment must be viewed through the legal framework of the Prosecutor General's Office, under Article 5 of OUG 31/2002 and Article 397 of the Criminal Code. To this end, I have formulated a research instrument which is summarized in Table 3.

Theoretical framework: Milestones in the academic definition of European and Romanian fascism

Addressing the core issue of the resurgence of Legionary ideology in contemporary Romania requires, above all, a comparative analysis between the accusations brought by the Prosecutor General's Office

and an established historical definition, both sociological and political, of European fascism and Romanian Legionary ideology. To begin with, it's essential to note that Romania's most prominent fascist movement, though not the only one, is the Legionary Movement, which operated under several different names throughout its existence (Legion of the Archangel Michael, Iron Guard, "Everything for the Country" Party). Therefore, an academically accepted and widely shared definition of European and Romanian fascism must be identified in the specialized academic literature, which has experienced a significant revival in recent decades, especially through analytical and comparative contributions that attempt to define the nature, structure and intensity of fascist regimes.

The specialized academic literature provides solid conceptual foundations for the theoretical delimitation of fascist ideology and regimes in Western Europe. Woolf (1969) proposes a comparative reading of fascisms, emphasizing their structural differences. Griffin (1995) formulates one of the most influential operational definitions of fascism – paligenetic ultranationalism – which emphasizes the national mythical regeneration. Thurlow (1999) contributes to the consolidation of political scientific analysis centered on organizational forms, public discourse and the relationship with liberal democracy, with a comparative analysis of the internal functioning of fascist movements. Mann (2004a) offers a sociological interpretation of fascism as a radical form of violent nationalism, proposing comparative variables regarding the exercise of power and repression (in Italy, Germany, Austria, Hungary, Romania and Spain). Bosworth (2010) reassesses the Italian fascist regime, insisting on institutional continuities and the complexity of the relationship between leader, state and ideology, revealing both doctrinal features and those related to political practice.

Feldman, Turda, and Georgescu (2008) pave the way for a regional interpretation, emphasizing the distinctiveness of fascist movements in Central and Eastern Europe, with particularly noteworthy cases in Greece, Serbia, Ukraine, Croatia, and Hungary. In a similar comparative vein, Iordachi (2009) contends that fascism in Eastern Europe frequently emerged from a fusion of traditional authoritarianism and radical ideological mobilization.

Regarding Romanian fascism, Volovici (1991) analyses the anti-Semitic ideology of the interwar intelligentsia and its role in the radicalization of public discourse. Veiga (1993) provides a detailed synthesis of the Legionary Movement, highlighting its internal dynamics and its positioning within the broader European context. Ioanid (1994) documents the mechanisms of repression and extermination of the Romanian state during the Holocaust. Heinen (1999) examines the Iron Guard as a distinct form of radical, paramilitary fascism in Eastern Europe. Ionescu and Rotman (2003) underscore the authorities' complicity and ambiguity in responding to Legionary violence. Clark (2015) explores the symbolic and ritual mobilization of Legionary ideology through an approach shaped by theories of charisma and collective identity. Ornea (2015) presents a cultural critique of the interwar legacy of far-right intellectuals. Bucur (2019) and Grecu (2023) contribute to reshaping political memory, within legionary contexts, in Greater Romania. Iordachi (2023) resumes the typological analysis of Romanian far-right regimes in a comparative framework. Müller (2025) evaluates the national-legionary dictatorship in the context of collaboration with Nazi Germany. Schmitt (2022) and Niculescu (2017) offer biographical and critical interpretations of the legionary leader Corneliu Zelea Codreanu. Deletant (2008) and Harward (2024) deal with Romania's involvement in the Holocaust, with an emphasis on the crimes committed by the military occupation in Transnistria, demonstrating the systematic criminal nature of the Antonescu regime. Finally, the Final Report of the International Commission on the Holocaust in Romania (2004) remains the fundamental reference work on the responsibility of the Romanian state in extermination policies. The documentation charging Georgescu prepared by the Prosecutor General's Office for the Public Ministry's Indictment dated July 1, 2025 must not be

overlooked, as it synthesizes some of the most valuable Romanian and international theoretical contributions on fascist and Legionary ideology.

General methodological framework

Given the considerations outlined above, the present study employs a mixed methodology (structured around three different types of scientific analysis), legal (Table 1), doctrinal (Table 3) and comparative-evaluative (Table 2), which allows the analysis of (interwar) Romanian fascism and (contemporary) neo-fascism in the European context.

Methodological framework for the legal analysis. As indicated in the methodological commentary following Table 1, I sought to assess (through a legal lens) whether the indictment by the General Prosecutor's Office fulfils the conditions of typicality, in line with contemporary criminal doctrine (Mihail Udriou, 2025a, 2025b, 2025c, 2025d, 2025e, 2025f, and 2025g), for the crime defined in Article 5 of OUG 31/2002, which criminalizes the promotion, in public, of the cult of persons guilty of committing crimes of genocide against humanity and war crimes, as well as the promotion, in public, of fascist, legionary, racist or xenophobic ideas, concepts or doctrines. This offense is punishable by imprisonment ranging from 3 months to 3 years, together with the prohibition of certain rights.

The typicality of the criminal offense involves verifying its constituent elements (objective and subjective components, active and passive subjects, consequences), in accordance with criminal law doctrine, which emphasizes the principle of legality (*nullum crimen sine lege*) and the requirement for clarity and predictability of criminal legislation (Article 1, Paragraph 5 of the Romanian Constitution and Article 7 of the European Convention on Human Rights). Contemporary doctrine (Mihail Udriou, 2025a, 2025b, 2025c, 2025d, 2025e, 2025f, and 2025g) stresses the strict interpretation of special criminal legislation to prevent abuse, with a focus on intent and abstract social danger.

An analysis of the objective components, namely the material element, legal object, and consequences, reveals the typicality of the criminal offense under Article 5 of OUG 31/2002. The act involves the unequivocal public promotion, via channels accessible to an indeterminate audience (such as online interviews, public speeches, and internet posts), of the cult of certain figures (Codreanu, Antonescu) and Legionary ideas (including implicit racism and explicit authoritarianism). Such promotion creates a risk of incitement to extremism, as it may contribute to radicalization, thereby endangering national security and democratic order, the latter being fundamental social values protected by criminal law. Furthermore, Mihail Udriou (2025a, 2025b, 2025c, 2025d, 2025e, 2025f, and 2025g) highlights that offenses of this kind pertain to an abstract societal threat – as seen in this instance – rather than result in direct, physical harm.

The verification of the subjective element – such as intent or culpability – also confirms the criminal typicality of the acts for which Georgescu is indicted. These were committed with direct intent (*dolus*), demonstrated through repetition and contextual evidence, reflecting a deliberate and conscious pursuit of an extremist political objective – namely, incitement to nationalist adherence and violence. Despite the criminal typicality, until a final and irrevocable court ruling is issued, Georgescu fully benefits from the constitutional presumption of innocence, the doctrinal protection of the Venice Commission (which warns against risks to freedom of expression), and the necessary judicial review of proportionality, as required by the European Court of Human Rights, between the clarity of the offense and democratic necessity.

Methodological framework for the comparative-evaluative analysis. Upon a legal confirmation as to Georgescu's affinity to the Legionary Movement, it becomes essential to examine Romanian interwar fascism within the broader European context. This helps to underscore the profound danger

such a political stance which is otherwise historically culpable and legally condemned may pose to democratic society as a whole, and to Romanian democracy in particular. As demonstrated in the preceding section, there is a scholarly consensus that fascism takes distinct forms depending on specific national contexts. This comparative dimension has been explored in Table 2. It is important to interpret this observation as indicating that, while the essence of fascism is universally criminal and repressive, the degree of violence it entails varies across different societies.

Therefore, this table includes a comparative analysis, by the degree of systemic violence, of European fascist regimes (including the Legionary and Antonescian ideologies) and proposes a doctrinal scoring, using a semi-quantitative evaluation grid, with an approach inspired by the methodology of Weberian ideal types, reinterpreted, readapted and reconstructed, in the context of European fascism, following the works published by Payne (1996), Linz (2000), and Paxton (2004). We measured the extreme right-wing political regimes, in terms of systemic repression (by irremediably affecting people's negative rights and freedoms), based on an evaluation grid with the following five analytical variables: authoritarian political control; racial ideology; repression of the opposition; systemic crimes; military expansionism. Each of these five dimensions was assessed on a scale of 1 to 10, by means of doctrinal scoring, with the following measurement levels: low (1), moderate (2-4), high (5-7), extreme (8-9), total (10). For the assessment scale measuring the level of systemic crimes, we employed the following range: low (1), moderate (2-4), high (5-7), pogromic (8-9), and genocidal (10).

These variables were extracted from research considered canonical for the study of European fascism using the structured focused comparison method (George and Bennett, 2005). Each dimension (measured from 1 to 10) was developed, selected and defined based on comparative empirical research – on the manifestations of fascism in interwar and postwar Europe, but also during the Second World War, carried out mainly by Mazower (2000), Mann (2004b) and Snyder (2010). Additionally, to maintain consistency in scoring the regimes, we relied on scientifically validated sources to describe the systemic criminality inherent in fascist political repression (Burleigh and Wippermann, 1991; Kershaw, 2008; Kallis, 2009). Table 2 presents a semi-quantitative ordinal scale with descriptive labels, constructed using qualitative criteria to evaluate the level of systemic criminality in each European fascist regime between 1922 and 1975. Every effort has been made to ensure that this assessment is not arbitrary, but rather historically grounded, methodologically valid, and measurably comparative.

Methodological framework for the doctrinal analysis. Table 3 presents a comparative assessment, using a numerical scale from 1 to 10, of the degree of overlap (where 1 indicates no overlap and 10 represents complete overlap) between the material acts for which Georgescu is indicted by the General Prosecutor's Office (according to Article 5 of OUG 31/2002 and Article 397 of the Criminal Code) and the historical doctrinal characteristics of classical European fascism (in particular, the Italian Mussolini ideology and Spanish Francoism). The assessment of the doctrinal features of classical European fascism is done through the structured focused comparison method (George and Bennett, 2005), which involves the application of a common scoring grid on analytical variables obtained by focusing on relevant and general aspects. The analytical variables (classical doctrinal features) are: (1) radical mono-identitarian nationalism, (2) charismatic and providential authoritarianism, (3) military dictatorship or one-party system, (4) state corporatism (with politically directed economy), (5) militarism and politically instrumented violence, (6) xenophobia and racism (institutionalized anti-Semitism), (7) anti-democratic ideology and anti-parliamentarianism, (8) propaganda and media control, (9) palingenesis (creation of the “new man”), (10) ideologically instrumented mysticism, and (11) anti-Marxism (anti-socialism, anti-egalitarianism, anti-materialism).

Each of these variables receives a score between 1 and 10, and the average provides an aggregate indicator of adhesion to fascism: low (1), moderate (2-4), high (5-7), extreme (8-9), total (10).

This comparative doctrinal scoring method ensures methodological coherence and comparability across cases. When analyzing the Romanian case, the analysis is supported by the specialized literature on Legionary ideology (Clark, 2015; Iordachi, 2023) and Antonescu ideology (Deletant, 2008; Harward, 2024), complemented by major works on the logic of extermination and fascist ideologies in Europe (Snyder, 2010; Mann, 2004a; Mann, 2004b). Table 3 is, therefore, the result of applying a method derived from the classical doctrinal analysis of generic fascism (Griffin, 1993; Paxton, 2004; Gentile, 2006).

Research results: legal analysis

As previously emphasized, the Prosecutor General's Office found the defendant, Călin Georgescu, guilty of the criminal offense outlined in Article 5 of OUG 31/2002, in conjunction with Article 35, Paragraph 1 of the Criminal Code. This refers to the public promotion of the cult of individuals convicted of genocide, crimes against humanity, and war crimes, as well as the public dissemination of fascist, legionary, racist, or xenophobic ideas, conceptions, or doctrines, carried out in a continuous manner. Specifically, Georgescu is indicted for having publicly promoted – between June 16, 2020 and May 16, 2025, at various intervals and under the same criminal resolution (June 16, 2020, September 2020, October 2, 2021, September 1, 2024 and May 16, 2025) – fascist, legionary and xenophobic ideas, conceptions and doctrines, such as the mass mobilization of the nation for its regeneration and rebirth through palingenesis (the creation of a “new man”), the propagation of Orthodox Christian mysticism, the implicit acceptance of certain violent means, the justification of the emergence of a charismatic, predestined, and authoritarian leader, and the excessive glorification of the historical past in contrast to the present situation, which is portrayed as profoundly damaging to the dignity of the national community and placing it in a state of victimhood due to the actions of enemies of the state, artificially identified as external state actors, expression of populist ultranationalism. The indictment also cites Georgescu’s cultivation of Marshal Ion Antonescu’s legacy, despite his definitive conviction for war crimes, portraying him as a national hero and imitating his speech, gestures, and tone. Additionally, Georgescu performed the legionary salute during a speech delivered to protesters opposing COVID-19 restrictions in University Square, Bucharest, on October 2, 2021 (Indictment issued by the Public Prosecutor’s Office on July 1, 2025).

I shall now provide a brief review of the established facts¹⁵. Georgescu made a series of laudatory remarks about several historical figures from the political past of the Legionary Movement, such as Corneliu Zelea Codreanu, Ion Antonescu, Ion Gavrilă Ogoranu, Ioan Ianolide, Ioan Moța and Vasile Marin, Gheorghe Cantacuzino-Grănicerul, Nicoleta Nicolescu, Gheorghe Manu, Iustin Pârvu, Mircea Vulcănescu, Petre Țuțea, Nae Ionescu, Constantin Noica, Mircea Eliade, Emil Cioran, and Lucian Blaga. More serious than the homage paid to all these Legionary figures is the self-referential allusion made by Georgescu when he suggests that only a man of integrity (as he considers himself) will carry forward “this holy light of love for nation, land, and language” inspired by the Legionary Movement

¹⁵ Details of the material acts incriminated by the Prosecutor General's Office against candidate Călin Georgescu can be found in the Public Ministry Indictment dated July 1, 2025. The document was prepared by Chief Prosecutor Marius Iacob of the Criminal Investigation Service within the Criminal Investigation Division of the Prosecutor's Office attached to the High Court of Cassation and Justice, in case file no. 2226/221/P/2023/d1 (https://www.luju.ro/static/files/2025/iulie/01/rechizitoriu_calin_georgescu.pdf).

and its leader, Corneliu Zelea Codreanu. In other words, Georgescu portrays himself as continuing the thought and action of Zelea Codreanu. In a television broadcast, he quoted in full a phrase from his political mentor (Codreanu) with an evidently self-referential tone: “He who fights, even alone, against a band of strong men, for his nation, his country, and for God, will never be defeated.” This quote is taken directly from the Codreanu’s book *For the Legionaries*: “From that moment, the belief took root in me and will never leave me: that he who fights, even alone, for God and his nation, will never be defeated” (Codreanu, 1936, 22). Additionally, Georgescu closely imitated not only the words, but also the gestures (specifically, the Legionary salute) and the tone of Marshal Ion Antonescu from his speech delivered at the Great Legionary Assembly on October 6, 1940: “Through peace and faith, through order and unity, through work and love, with God ahead” (Indictment issued by the Public Prosecutor’s Office on July 1, 2025). These electoral comments, which express praise for Legionary and Antonescian ideologies, were legally classified and analyzed in Table 1 in relation to contemporary criminal doctrine (Mihail Udrouiu, 2025a, 2025b, 2025c, 2025d, 2025e, 2025f, and 2025g), in order to verify the criminal typology defined in Article 5 of OUG 31/2002.

Table 1. Legal evaluation of whether the conditions of criminal typology are met under Article 5 of OUG 31/2002, concerning Călin Georgescu’s public promotion of fascist ideologies and the cult of individuals convicted of war crimes.

Analyzed element	Fulfilment of the analyzed element	Detailed argument
The alleged acts (the five material acts) occurred in public	Yes	Speeches in public squares, on TV, in online interviews, all within the public domain.
The alleged five material acts represent political promotion rather than merely conveying a personal interpretation of historical events	Yes	Repeated use, laudatory language, and precise imitation of convicted leaders within politically significant settings.
The alleged five material acts involve promoting the cult of persons convicted of war crimes	Yes	Antonescu, Zelea Codreanu, Moța and Marin are repeatedly presented as national heroes.
There is either direct or indirect intent behind the commission of the alleged five material acts	Yes	Coherent language, explicit idealization, programmatic argumentation.
Continued pattern (criminal repetitiveness) of the alleged five material acts	Yes	Five material acts, in different years, with the same ideological content.

Methodological remarks: This table serves a normative role, intended to assess whether the conditions for the criminal offense outlined in Article 5 of OUG 31/2002 – concerning the promotion of the cult of individuals convicted of war crimes – have been met. The method used is deductive, based on the analysis of the constitutive elements of the criminal offense (objective and subjective side), in accordance with contemporary criminal doctrine. This analysis is correlated with the criminal, legal and doctrinal classification of the glorified persons (Ion Antonescu, Corneliu Zelea Codreanu) as war criminals (1946) and traitors (1938), according to the final court sentences, the normative acts in force and the established historical research.

I carried out a legal analysis of the circumstances in which the acts charged by the Prosecutor General's Office against Georgescu meet the constitutive elements of the crime in Article 5 of OUG 31/2002 regarding the public promotion of fascist ideologies and the cult of persons convicted of war crimes. All the conditions of typicality set out in Article 5 of OUG 31/2002 are fulfilled, so that it may be concluded that the acts charged against Călin Georgescu are repetitive, publicly expressed, ideologically consistent, and clearly aimed at the indirect yet systematic promotion of a fascist ideology and the veneration of leaders (fascists and Legionaries) criminally convicted of genocide against humanity and war crimes.

Research results: comparative-evaluative analysis

Table 2 holds particular political and historical importance, as it illustrates the high level of systemic criminality associated with Romanian fascist movements: The Legionary (1940-1941) and Antonescian ideology (1941-1945) represent radical forms of European fascism, surpassed in systemic criminality only by German Nazism. Alongside the Croatian Ustasha (Ustaša) (1941-1945) and Hungarian Szálasi's ideology (1944-1945), the Legionary Movement (1940-1941) and Antonescu Regime (1941-1945) occupied a brutal second place, just behind German Nazism, in the hierarchy of the most uncompromising and repressive national expressions of European fascism.

A defining feature of both the Legionary and Antonescian ideology was their strong religious mysticism rooted in Orthodox Christianity, which served as an ideological justification for purges and mass exterminations. Legionary and Antonescian ideology functioned as a political religion in the fullest sense of the term, transforming the murder of Jews into a macabre article of faith. For this reason, Romania experienced, around the time of World War II, the second most virulent form of anti-Semitism in Europe, measured by the intensity of political repression. Unlike the racially driven anti-Semitism of German Nazism, Romania's was religiously motivated, making it theologically aberrant. Legionary and Antonescian ideology, alongside the Croatian Ustasha (Ustaša) (1941-1945) and Hungarian Szálasi's ideology (1944-1945), were among the most radically anti-Semitic far-right movements in Europe, nearly as extreme as German Nazism, though not equally exterminatory. Therefore, the Legionary and Antonescian propaganda promoted by Călin Georghescu in relation to some of the most criminal European fascist regimes constitutes an extreme manifestation of political culpability.

The table contains an ordinal scale, with descriptive labels, developed on the basis of qualitative criteria (defined according to five fundamental political dimensions): authoritarian political control (suppression of political pluralism), racial ideology (official implementation of racism), repression of the opposition (exercising violence against domestic political opponents), systemic crimes (mass extermination of minorities, such as pogroms and genocide), and military expansionism (external territorial aggression through territorial annexationism). Each of these five dimensions was assessed, by uniform political scoring, on a scale of 1 to 10, with the following measurement levels: low (1), moderate (2-4), high (5-7), extreme (8-9), total (10). The scale measuring the level of systemic crimes is the following: low (1), moderate (2-4), high (5-7), pogromic (8-9), genocidal (10). For each fascist regime, a general arithmetic mean was computed, with equal weights for all scores, leading to the following classification: hybrid fascism (1-3.9), classical fascism (4-6.9), radical fascism (7-9.9), and totalitarian fascism (10). The fascist regimes are ordered in ascending order, according to the general mean and ideal typology, from the most moderate to the most extremist, that is, from hybrid fascism (which contains fascist elements only partially and of reduced intensity) and classical fascism (which must be defined by coherent doctrinal and institutional patterns) to radical fascism (with a high level of political violence, pogrom racism and territorial expansionism) and totalitarian fascism (Nazism is the canonical example for the absolute and complete form of fascism, which involves absolute control over society, genocidal racism, planned extermination, imperialist expansionism).

The typology in Table 2, resulting from the comparative assessment of European fascisms, classifies the regimes into four distinct categories, differentiated according to their dictatorial and criminal nature. The classification is based on measurable criteria, such as the degree of authoritarianism of the regime, the official existence of racial ideology, the repression of political opposition, the involvement of the regime in systematic crimes and annexationist aggression.

Table 2. The comparative evaluation of fascist regimes in Europe (1922-1975), based on five analytical variables measuring the intensity of systemic repression.

Political name of the fascist regime (leader), country (historical period)	Level of authoritarian political control	Level of political racism	Level of repression against political opposition	Level of systemic crimes	Level of military aggression, external expansionism and territorial annexationism	Average score, classification in the typology of fascist regimes, analytical comments
<i>Estado Novo</i> (Salazar and Caetano) Portugal (1933-1974)	3 moderate	1 low	2 moderate	1 low	2 moderate	1.8 (hybrid fascism) Corporatist authoritarian regime, without racist or expansionist dimensions. Has committed no systemic crimes.
<i>The August 4th Regime</i> (Metaxas) Greece (1936-1941)	5 high	2 moderate	4 moderate	2 moderate	2 moderate	3.0 (hybrid fascism) Regime influenced by Italian fascism, without racial policies or expansionist ambitions.
<i>Sanacja</i> (Pilsudski) Poland (1926-1939)	6 high	3 moderate	5 high	3 moderate	2 moderate	3.8 (hybrid fascism) Militarized authoritarian regime, with nationalist elements, but without doctrinal racism or overt expansionist policies.
<i>Francoism</i> (Franco) Spain (1939-1975)	6 high	4 moderate	5 high	4 moderate	2 moderate	4.2 (classical fascism) Authoritarian clerical-militarist regime, severe repression, but without expansionism or genocidal policies.
<i>Austro-fascism</i> (Dollfuss and Schuschnigg) Austria (1933-1938)	7 high	3 moderate	6 high	3 moderate	2 moderate	4.2 (classical fascism) Clerical-nationalist regime inspired by Italian corporatism. Political repression with no major systemic crimes or expansionism.
<i>The Vichy Regime</i> (Pétain) France (1940-1944)	7 high	7 high	6 high	7 high	3 moderate	6.0 (classical fascism) Puppet regime and collaborator with Nazi Germany, involved in deportations, with racial and repressive policies.
<i>Mussolini's Fascism</i> (Mussolini) Kingdom of Italy (1922-1943)	7 high	5 high	6 high	4 moderate	9 extreme	6.2 (classical fascism) Institutionalized fascist regime; racial accents since 1938, notable military expansionism.

Horthysm (Horthy) Hungary (1920-1944)	7 high	7 high	7 high	7 high	6 high	6.6 (classical fascism) Expansionist authoritarian regime; participation in the invasion of the USSR, anti-Jewish purge.
Slovak clerical-fascist regime (Jozef Tiso) Slovak State (1939-1945)	8 extreme	9 extreme	8 extreme	9 pogromic	5 high	7.4 (radical fascism) Puppet regime; deportations and purges in collaboration with Nazi Germany.
Salò Regime (Mussolini) Italian Social Republic (1943-1945)	8 extreme	8 extreme	8 extreme	7 high	7 high	7.6 (radical fascism) Puppet regime of Nazi Germany, with racial policies and increased repression. Military collaboration with the Nazis.
National-Legionary State (Antonescu and Sima) Romania (1940-1941)	7 High	8 extreme	8 extreme	9 pogromic	6 high	7.6 (radical fascism) Violent insurrectionary regime; purges, pogroms, radical ideological control.
Antonescu military regime (Antonescu) Romania (1941-1944)	8 extreme	9 extreme	8 extreme	8 pogromic	7 high	8.0 (radical fascism) Fascist military regime, racial policies and crimes in Transnistria. Participation in the USSR invasion and the Holocaust.
Ustaša (Pavelić) Croatia (1941-1945)	9 extreme	10 total	9 extreme	10 genocidal	6 high	8.8 (radical fascism) Terrorist and genocidal regime; extermination of Serbs, Roma and Jews.
Arrow Cross Party regime (Szálasi) Hungary (1944-1945)	9 extreme	9 extreme	9 extreme	10 genocidal	7 high	8.8 (radical fascism) Exterminatory regime, in the service of Nazi Germany; deportations and violent internal repression.
Nazism (Hitler) Germany (1933-1945)	10 total	10 total	10 total	10 genocidal	10 total	10 (totalitarian fascism) Absolute model of totalitarian fascism: planned extermination system, total control, Holocaust, world war.

Methodological remarks: The regimes have been classified and defined, in general, using the following sources: Burleigh and Wippermann (1991) for systemic crimes and institutional racism; Clark (2015) and Iordachi (2023) for Romanian Legionary ideology and the cult of Corneliu Zelea Codreanu; Deletant (2008) and Harward (2024) for the racial repression characteristic of Romanian Antonescian ideology; George and Bennett (2005) for the structured and focused comparison method; Griffin (1993 and 2005) for generic fascism understood as a modern political religion; Kallis (2009) for the criminality of collaborationist political regimes with collaborating Nazi Germany; Kershaw (2008) for the Holocaust and the criminal decisions of Nazi Germany; Linz (2000) for the typology of fascist political regimes; Mann (2004b) for the explanation of the genocidal and pogrom dimensions; Mazower (2000) for the comparative analysis of fascist regimes; Paxton (2004) for the definition of doctrinal and comparative grids; Payne (1996) for the definition of fascist regimes and the degree of political radicalization; Snyder (2010) for mass murders in fascist Europe

The four archetypal forms of fascist regimes (listed from lightness to harshness, on the scale of political violence) are the following: (1) hybrid fascism¹⁶ (protofascism); (2) classical fascism¹⁷ (moderate); (3) radical fascism¹⁸ (extermination); and (4) totalitarian fascism¹⁹ (genocidal Nazism). The fact that the National-Legionary State - Romania (rated on the political violence scale with an average score of 7.6 out of 10) and Antonescu's Romania (rated with an average score of 8.0 out of 10) experienced a form of radical fascism, with exterminatory repression, placing it immediately after German Nazism in terms of criminal intensity, makes the contemporary electoral propaganda by Călin Georgescu in favor of such a political regime all the more culpable in terms of criminal liability.

Research results: doctrinal analysis

The final part of the presentation is dedicated to analyzing the public behavior (for which Georgescu is indicted by the General Prosecutor's Office) and the comparative evaluation of Georgescu's discourse through historical overlap with the main doctrinal features of classical European fascism. Specifically, we refer to the Italian (Mussolini) and Spanish (Franco) versions of fascism, as synthesized in Table 2. A doctrinal comparison with Romanian Legionary fascism is theoretically unnecessary, since it represents a radical form of fascism, marked by pogromic manifestations and extreme political repression under a strongly dictatorial regime – a situation that cannot be directly attributed to Georgescu. Therefore, regarding Article 5 of OUG 31/2002 (Legionary and Antonescian propaganda) and Article 397 of the Criminal Code (attempted coup d'état), we will examine in Table 3 whether fascist doctrine is defining for Georgescu's political behavior.

The table employs a semi-quantitative doctrinal assessment using a grid of 11 typological features characteristic of classical European fascism, specifically referencing Italian Mussolini ideology and Spanish Francoism, chosen via the structured focused comparison method (George and Bennett, 2005). The evaluation of each analytical variable is made on a numerical scale from 1 to 10. The degree

¹⁶ Hybrid fascism (or protofascism) refers to authoritarian regimes influenced by fascism, but which do not entirely conform to the ideological and structural features of classical fascism (for instance, protofascism often lacks a single ruling party). Such regimes incorporate practices rooted in fascism – like political repression and militant nationalism – yet maintain certain aspects of the traditional order, sometimes even preserving a fragile appearance of democracy or liberalism.

¹⁷ Classical (moderate) fascism refers to the fascist regimes themselves, generally based on a single party (de facto or de jure), a totalitarian ideology (with practices of moderate severity), and clear political repression, but without systematic extermination. These are criminal regimes that eliminate political opponents (without ethnic or racial discrimination) through covert police methods – typically involving arbitrary arrests, as well as crimes that appear to be common law offenses but are ideologically motivated. The state is organized according to corporatist principles, with strict control over civil society.

¹⁸ Radical (extermination-based) fascism refers to regimes characterized by systematic ethnic purging, extreme political violence, and a violently ultranationalist ideology, frequently including an explicit racial dimension. Such regimes often collaborate militarily with Hitler's Germany and display ideological and political subordination to the Nazi regime. This form of fascism is marked by the systematic use of terror, mass purges, the extermination of opponents, institutionalized racism, and either an alliance with or imitation of Nazism.

¹⁹ Totalitarian fascism (genocidal Nazism) is the absolute extreme form of fascist totalitarianism, characterized by a systematized racial ideology, policies of mass extermination, and total control over social, political, and cultural life. German Nazism is the most criminal version of fascism and embodies the peak of state violence in modern Europe, through the mass extermination of Jews (the Holocaust), concentration camps, mass racial cleansing, and total war. The only example of such a totalitarian fascist regime with strategically planned genocidal repression is the Germany of Führer Adolf Hitler (1933–1945).

of overlap (where 1 means no overlap and 10 means absolute overlap) between the material acts for which Georgescu is indicted by the Prosecutor General's Office (according to Article 5 of OUG 31/2002 and Article 397 of the Criminal Code) and the historical doctrinal characteristics of classical European fascism (in particular, Italian Mussolini ideology and Spanish Francoism) is comparatively evaluated, having the following measurement levels: low (1), moderate (2-4), high (5-7), extreme (8-9), total (10).

Table 3. Comparative evaluation of the degree of overlap between the material acts for which Călin Georgescu is indicted by the General Prosecutor's Office and the classical characteristics of European fascism.

Doctrinal feature of classical European fascism	Material acts for which Georgescu is indicted (Article 5, OUG 31/2002 and Article 397, the Criminal Code)	Analytical comment on the degree of overlap	Score (1-10)
Radical mono-identitarian nationalism	Glorification of the legionary legacy, the mythologization of national history, and the persistent invocation of sovereignty rooted in collective identity.	His discourse expresses a consistent and populist ultra-nationalism, with ethnocentric mythological valences.	9 (extreme)
Charismatic and providential authoritarianism	Self-presentation as a providential leader, symbolic evocation of Codreanu as a political model of a saviour-hero.	Cultivating one's own image as a political saviour is reminiscent of the mythology of the charismatic fascist leader.	9 (extreme)
Military dictatorship or one-party state	It does not propose the abolition of parties or the establishment of a single party. It maintains a formal democratic discourse.	It does not call for the abolition of pluralism, but it falls within a systemic critical rhetoric against democracy.	3 (moderate)
State corporatism with politically directed economy	Criticizes globalism, but does not propose a corporatist or politically controlled economic model.	Does not propose a classic fascist economic system and lacks doctrinal articulation in the economic area.	3 (moderate)
Militarism and politically orchestrated violence	No direct instigation of physical violence, although the political complicity with the armed mercenaries led by Horațiu Potra, who intended to storm the capital, after the annulment of the presidential elections, in order to overthrow the constitutional order, cause social disorder, threaten and intimidate journalists, politicians and public figures, is extremely aggravating.	The model of political action is entirely inspired by classical fascism, through direct links between the supreme political leader and paramilitary groups (such as the one led by Horațiu Potra), which planned the violent overthrow of the constitutional order, according to the Prosecutor General's Office.	8 (extreme)
Xenophobia, racism and institutionalized antisemitism	Praising criminally convicted legionary figures, without direct racist or antisemitic discourse, but with symbolic implication.	Indirectly, by glorifying historical antisemites, it symbolically legitimizes historical antisemitism.	6 (high)
Anti-democratic and anti-parliamentarian	Although he does not directly support the abolition of democracy, he is officially accused of complicity in an attempt to change the constitutional order.	The Prosecutor General's accusation of complicity in a coup d'état places him in a dangerous anti-democratic zone.	8 (extreme)
Propaganda and media control	Uses alternative channels (TikTok, YouTube), without demanding control or claiming censorship of traditional media.	Lack of institutional propaganda, uses viral exposure, not classic fascist mechanisms.	2 (moderate)

Palingenesis (creation of the “new man”)	Evokes national regeneration and the call to dignity, without clear ideological institutionalization.	Constantly uses the rhetoric of regeneration, but without a clear ideological or organizational apparatus.	6 (high)
Ideologically instrumented Mysticism	Constant discourse based on Orthodox mysticism, Dacian ethnocentrism, spiritual influence of Zalmoxis, political inspiration having as its source divine energies.	Elements of Christian and pre-Christian religiosity are the pivot of the political discourse, a defining feature for Legionary ideology, a radical form of European fascism.	8 (extreme)
Anti-Marxism (anti-socialism, anti-egalitarianism, anti-materialism)	No anti-Marxist doctrinal statements, but praises far-right leaders without a leftist ideological context.	The absence of an anti-communist and anti-proletarian doctrinal discourse limits the overlap at this level.	2 (moderate)

Methodological remarks: The sources indicated in the methodological remarks in Table 2 are also relevant here.

Table 3 illustrates how the use of a semi-quantitative doctrinal evaluation method, structured around a grid of 11 typological features of classical fascism, enabled the identification of a partial yet significant alignment between interwar far-right ideology and the public expressions of the sovereigntist candidate. This analysis emphasizes the extent of ideological overlap, quantified by an average score of 5.8 out of 10, between the political elements articulated by Georgescu during his electoral campaign (as filtered through the scrutiny of the Prosecutor General's Office) and the core doctrinal principles of Italian and Spanish fascism. Consequently, the score of 5.8 out of 10 reflects a partial yet notable convergence, positioning Georgescu at the lower threshold of the ideological risk zone linked to classical fascism, while falling short of fulfilling the full criteria for institutionalized right-wing extremism. The Legionary ideology adopted by Georgescu is located at the upper limit of the moderate degree, respectively at the lower limit of the high degree, in relation to the characteristics of classical European fascism (Italian Mussolini ideology and Spanish Francoism).

The highest levels of overlap were recorded in the dimensions of radical ultranationalism, charismatic authoritarianism, religious mystification and symbolic support (through complicity) of violence as an instrument of political action. In contrast, the defining elements of institutionalized fascism are missing, such as systematic paramilitary organization, a coherent corporatist economic model or the claim of a one-party system. This differentiation is essential, as it shows us that it is impossible, for now, to label Georgescu *stricto sensu* as a fascist (in the historical-institutional sense of the term used in the classical ideological version).

Concluding remarks

Georgescu advances a discourse that symbolically reactivates elements of classical fascism, reconfigured within a neo-integrated doctrinal framework, yet functions disruptively in political terms, which may pose a potential threat to the stability of Romania's democratic environment. From a legal point of view (Table 1), however, this indirect form of political promotion, especially by evoking and idealizing figures convicted of war crimes, may attract criminal liability under Article 5 of OUG 31/2002, which sanctions not only violent instigation, but also the public promotion of fascist ideologies or the cult of persons guilty of genocide and war crimes. In addition, pursuant to Article 397 of the Criminal Code, political complicity with Horațiu Potra may result in the criminal indictment of Georgescu for crimes committed against the constitutional order. It is self-evident that, until a final conviction is delivered, the constitutional presumption of innocence remains fully applicable. Accordingly, this analysis can adopt a more severe interpretive stance only after Georgescu has been formally indicted and, potentially, convicted, especially in relation to the crime of complicity in the attempted coup.

However, beyond the legal argumentation advanced in Table 1, the political propaganda made by Georgescu in favor of two of the most radical European fascist regimes, which implemented a form of dictatorial, exterminatory repression in Romania ranking immediately after German Nazism in terms of criminal intensity, namely Legionary ideology (assessed on the political violence scale with an average score of 7.6 out of 10) and Antonescian ideology (assessed with an average score of 8.0 out of 10), aggravates the perpetrator's criminal and political liability (Table 2).

From a doctrinal perspective (Table 3), the overlap between the elements of political ideology present in Georgescu's electoral campaign (as filtered through the criminal lens of the Prosecutor General's Office) and the classical version of European fascism (Italian Mussolini ideology and Spanish Francoism) indicates an average convergence score of 5.8 out of 10. This implies that the neo-Legionary ideology practiced by Georgescu is positioned at the upper end of the moderate range, and at the lower end of the high range, in relation to the characteristics of classical European fascism (Italian Mussolini ideology and Spanish Francoism).

Nevertheless, there is one essential remark to be made: for a political harlequin like Georgescu, clad in a jumpsuit of multicolored political diamonds, stitched together with every imaginable goofiness, his support for Legionary ideology is merely one patch in his patchwork. Thus, for a presidential buffoon like Georgescu, the recitals drawn from the legionary repertoire represent merely the enactment of one of his roles. Admittedly, these acts carry criminal undertones, especially considering that the Legionary and Antonescu ideologies were radical manifestations of European fascism, but I believe this theatrical lens is the most appropriate way to interpret Georgescu's legionary Potemkin spectacle.

In conclusion, this study offers an original scientific contribution in two key areas: first, by applying a semi-quantitative analytical method to a contemporary electoral case, Romania, 2024, it introduces a novel approach to examining right-wing political extremism in post-communist Europe; second, it advances legal-doctrinal interpretive frameworks for analyzing radical discourses which, though not institutionalized, may carry both political and criminal implications. I consider this approach establishes a constructive analytical framework for examining the symbolic reactivation of emerging neo-fascism in Central and Eastern European countries and provides future directions for research into the relationship between political ideology and historical-legal responsibility. Standardized grids for assessing the impact of extremist discourse could be successfully used in the future by state institutions charged with protecting the constitution and defending democracy.

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